

INFLUENCE OF THE IMPREGNATION RATE AND COMPRESSION MOLDING CONDITIONS ON THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF CFRTP

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Keywords: *CFRTP, Polypropylene, Impregnation rate, Molding pressure*

1 Introduction

In recent years, environmental and energy issues resulting from increase of the energy consumption in the world are aggravating [1][2]. At present, approximately half of the world's energy is consumed by OECD countries. Considering the population growth and economic development in non-OECD countries in the future, it is urgent that we take some measures. Although there are various measures, replacing the conventional materials of automobile with CFRP (carbon fiber reinforced plastics) and carrying out a weight saving is expected as an effective measure. However, because of the problem of molding speed, costs, and recycling, it is difficult to apply conventional CFRTPS (carbon fiber reinforced thermosetting resins) to mass-production automobiles. Therefore, studies of CFRTP (carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastics) are undergoing, since CFRTP has advantages such as easy molding and recycling compared to CFRTPS.

In especially, for increasing productivity and reducing the molding costs, related CFRTP techniques for automotive parts has been developed and paid attention. However, detailed studies for the optimal molding conditions of structural CFRTP have not been enough published, and car manufacturers are preparing to go home.

In anticipation of the application of CFRTP to mass-production automobiles, in this study, we would like to discuss about optimal relationship of T-P-t, that is, temperature, pressure and time, for molding, jointing and repairing. In especially, the pressure affects their

facilities directly. If a necessary pressure becomes smaller, size of machines for molding, jointing and repairing can become smaller, that leads to lower costs of capital investment [3][4]. Further, revealing the heating and melting conditions and holding time will contribute to design the production line of automobiles. A target of minimum pressure in jointing and repairing is to achieve the same mechanical properties as it would be molded in a press machine. Therefore we investigate an influence of the relationship of T-P-t on the mechanical properties to consider appropriate methods and conditions of molding, jointing and repairing. In addition, we would like to investigate influence of the impregnation rate of the substrate on the mechanical properties of CFRTP products.

2 Materials and molding methods

2.1 Materials

Two types of materials are used in this study. One is chopped carbon fiber tape reinforced thermoplastics (CTT) shown in Fig. 1 and the other is cross ply CFRTP shown in Fig. 2 They use the same carbon fiber UD tape whose V_f is 50% and resin is modified polypropylene.

CTT is composed of randomly dispersed chopped UD tapes, hence shows isotropy. And impregnation rate of the CTT substrate is sufficient because CTT must go through the pre-impregnation step at the manufacturing stage of the substrate. Hence this material is useful not only for high cycle molding

but complex shaped structural parts due to its high V_f and flow moldability. But there remains a problem for CAE that the variation of the mechanical properties becomes large in the case of small specimen, although the variation becomes small in the case of actual parts [5].

Cross ply is composed of laminated UD tape in the direction of the $[0^\circ/90^\circ]$. At the step of the lamination, impregnation rate of the cross ply substrate is not sufficient. These carbon fiber UD tape and CTT are provided by TOYOBO CO., LTD.

2.2 Molding methods

2.2.1 Heat and cool forming

Heat and cool forming, shown in Fig. 3, is conventional molding method of CFRTP performed in the mold all the steps of heating and melting, forming, cooling and solidification of the material.

In this study, the substrate was heated and melted for 15 min while applying to the substrate the pressure of 0.1 MPa in a mold, and the temperature was raised to 210 °C. After that, the substrate was cooled and molded at the same time, and holding time was set to 3 min.

2.2.2 Stamp forming

Stamp forming, shown in Fig. 4 is molding method in which the substrate is heated and melted outside of the mold and formed in the mold at constant temperature. Since we don't need to wait for a mold heating, molding cycle can be within 1 min, so it is promising as applicable molding method in the production line of automobiles.

In this study, the substrate was heated and melted 4 or 8 min outside of the mold, up to 210 °C by the far radiant heating by hot plate or infrared heater. Forming time in the mold was set to 1 min [5]-[12].

2.2.3 Preliminary impregnation process

In this study, the step of increasing the impregnation rate of the substrate prior to molding is defined as preliminary impregnation process. The pre-impregnation was performed in the process that the substrate before molding was held for 5 min at a pressure of 0.3 MPa and temperature of 200 °C in the mold, then cooled for 15 min.

3 Experimental procedure and results

Because of the problem regarding CTT's variation described above, first we made specimen using the cross ply substrate molded by changing the molding method, conditions and impregnation rate. Then, we performed three-point bending test to investigate the influence of each parameter on the mechanical properties [10][14]. Based on that result, we estimated the behavior of CTT specimen and conducted experiments to confirm that.

We conduct three point bending test with 10 specimens for CTT, and 5 specimens for cross ply CFRTP to obtain mechanical properties [5].

Further, to verify the actual degree of impregnation rate of specimen we used SEM (Scanning Electron Microscope) and observed fracture surface.

3.1 Heat and cool forming using cross ply

3.1.1 Molding conditions

We molded the cross ply substrate by heat and cool forming under different pressure, 1, 2, 3, 4, 8 MPa. Fig. 5 shows the relationship of T-P-t at heat and cool forming using CF/PP cross ply (8 MPa).

3.1.2 Result and discussion

Table 1 and Fig. 6 show the result of flexural strength on this experiment. As you see, there was no significant difference due to the difference in molding pressure. Even though the impregnation rate of the substrate is not sufficient, we can obtain the sufficient mechanical properties by heat and cool forming. This is because that resin is impregnated effectively by the pressure applied during heating regardless of the level of pressure. Figs. 7-11 are the SEM images of each specimen. Adhesion between resin and fiber is good for all specimens.

From a viewpoint of the initial investment cost of press machine, the low molding pressure can make machine smaller but the slow molding cycle causes the number of machine increase.

3.2 Stamp forming using cross ply

3.2.1 Molding conditions

We molded the cross ply substrate by stamp forming. The parameters were the impregnation rate, heating

and melting time, and molding pressure. Substrates without pre-impregnation process was molded with 1, 4 MPa molding pressure and 8 min heating and melting time, or 8, 18 MPa molding pressure and 4 min heating and melting time. On the other hand, the substrate with pre-impregnation process was molded with 4 MPa molding pressure and 8 min heating and melting time. Fig. 12 shows the relationships of T-P-t at stamp forming using CF/PP cross ply (4 MPa).

3.2.3 Result and discussion

Table. 2 and Fig. 13 show the result of flexural strength on this experiment. Even if molded by stamp forming over high pressure, the substrate that was not processed pre-impregnation didn't have sufficient mechanical properties. On the other hand, if molded by stamp forming with low pressure, the substrate that was processed pre-impregnation had sufficient mechanical properties. Consequently, even if molded with high pressure, it is considered that impregnation is not progressed when the pressurized time over melting point of PP is too short, so we need to impregnate the substrate enough before molding when performing the stamp forming. Figs. 14-18 are the SEM images of each specimen. Adhesion between resin and fiber is bad for the specimen without pre-impregnation, but good for the specimen with pre-impregnation.

3.3 Stamp forming using CTT

3.3.1 Molding conditions

We molded the CTT substrate by stamp forming under different pressure, 4, 11, 18 MPa. Fig.19 shows the relationship of T-P-t at stamp forming using CF/PP CTT (18 MPa).

3.3.2 Result and discussion

Table. 3 and Fig. 20 show the result of flexural strength on this experiment. Each specimen has sufficient mechanical properties. The CTT substrate processed pre-impregnation, as in the experiment using cross ply, has sufficient mechanical properties even if molded by stamp forming with low pressure. However, as variation of the flexural strength of 4MPa is higher than the other two, molding with around 10MPa or more is desirable when making

high quality products. Figs. 21-23 are the SEM images of each specimen. Adhesion between resin and fiber is good for all specimens. For reference, SEM image of CF/PP UD tape is shown in Fig. 24.

4 Conclusion

The most affective factor to the mechanical properties of CFRTP is impregnation rate of the resin, so it is necessary to perform sufficient impregnation at any stage of the substrate manufacturing, heating and melting, or molding. Stamp forming makes it possible to mold cycle faster, that is, minimization of cost of equipment, but using the substrate whose impregnation rate is not enough, we can't obtain the CFRTP products that have sufficient mechanical properties even if molded with high pressure (18 MPa).

Conversely, it is revealed in this study that if sufficient impregnation once performed before molding, CFRTP products that have enough mechanical properties can be obtained even though the molding pressure is comparatively low. Therefore, it can be said that if we progress the further study about efficient pre-impregnation process, we can significantly reduce the cost with respect to manufacturing process, such as miniaturization of the press machine, faster molding cycle.

In the case of compression molding for complex shape parts, molding pressure becomes higher in order to flow melted material along a mold. Hence the minimum pressure depends on a shape of parts. On the other hand, in the case of flat panel like bonnet and roof, minimum pressure depends on material, molding temperature and molding time. An area of such panel parts is usually large; hence this minimum pressure for plate molding is important since it determines the size of a press machine. Of course, longer molding time decreases minimum pressure, but longer molding time increases a production cycle time. And higher molding temperature decreases minimum pressure and molding time, but it's meaningless if it induces resin degradation. So we have to find an optimal T-P-t combination for each material.

Optimal T-P-t for jointing and repairing to obtain the maximum mechanical properties can be determined in the same manner.

Acknowledgements

This study was conducted as a part of Japanese METI-NEDO project "Development of sustainable hyper composite technology" since 2008fy. Authors would like to express sincerely appreciation to the project members who have provided valuable information and useful discussions.

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CTT substrate ($V_f = 50\%$)

Fig. 1 Illustration of CF/PP CTT.

Cross ply substrate ($V_f = 50\%$)

Fig. 2 Illustration of CF/PP cross ply.

Fig. 3 Procedure of heat and cool forming.

Fig. 4 Procedure of stamp forming.

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Fig. 5 Relationship of T-P-t at heat and cool forming for CF/PP cross ply (8 MPa).

Table 1 Flexural strength of CF/PP cross ply specimens on each molding pressure (heat and cool forming).

Molding pressure (MPa)	Flexural strength(MPa)		Coefficient of variation (%)
	Average	Standard deviation	
1	538	13	2.5
2	486	23	4.7
3	515	60	11.7
4	521	28	5.5
8	549	28	5.1

Fig. 6 Relationship between molding pressure and flexural strength of CF/PP cross ply specimens (heat and cool forming).

Fig. 7 Debonded CF of CF/PP cross ply specimen (heat and cool formed at 1 MPa).

Fig. 8 Debonded CF of CF/PP cross ply specimen (heat and cool formed at 2 MPa).

Fig. 9 Debonded CF of CF/PP cross ply specimen (heat and cool formed at 3 MPa).

Fig. 10 Debonded CF of CF/PP cross ply specimen (heat and cool formed at 4 MPa).

Fig. 11 Debonded CF of CF/PP cross ply specimen (heat and cool formed at 8 MPa).

Fig. 12 Relationship of T-P-t at stamp forming for CF/PP cross ply (4 MPa).

Table 2 Flexural strength of CF/PP cross ply specimens on each molding pressure (stamp forming).

Molding pressure (MPa)	Flexural strength(MPa)		Coefficient of variation (%)
	Average	Standard deviation	
1	230	18	8.0
4	312	30	9.7
8	169	16	9.5
18	210	30	14.2
4*	588	54	9.3

* pre-impregnated

Fig. 13 Relationship between molding pressure and flexural strength of stamp formed CF/PP cross ply specimens.

Fig. 14 Debonded CF of CF/PP cross ply specimen (stamp formed at 1 MPa without pre-impregnation).

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Fig. 15 Debonded CF of CF/PP cross ply specimen (stamp formed at 4 MPa without pre-impregnation).

Fig. 18 Debonded CF of CF/PP cross ply specimen (stamp formed at 4 MPa with pre-impregnation).

Fig. 16 Debonded CF of CF/PP cross ply specimen (stamp formed at 8 MPa without pre-impregnation).

Fig. 19 Relationship of T-P-t at stamp forming for CF/PP CTT (18 MPa).

Fig. 17 Debonded CF of CF/PP cross ply specimen (stamp formed at 18 MPa without pre-impregnation).

Table 3 Flexural strength of CF/PP CTT specimens on each molding pressure (stamp forming).

Molding pressure (MPa)	Flexural strength(MPa)		Coefficient of variation (%)
	Average	Standard deviation	
4	367	47	12.7
11	404	21	5.2
18	365	13	3.6

Fig. 20 Relationship between molding pressure and flexural strength of stamp formed CF/PP CTT specimens.

Fig. 23 Debonded CF of CF/PP CTT specimen (stamp formed at 18 MPa).

Fig. 21 Debonded CF of CF/PP CTT specimen (stamp formed at 4 MPa).

Fig. 24 SEM image of CF/PP UD tape.

Fig. 22 Debonded CF of CF/PP CTT specimen (stamp formed at 11 MPa).